

Gene	GeneBank accession no.	Organism
LiDGAT1	MF576159	<i>Lobosphaera incisa</i>
LiDGAT2.1	MH290880	<i>Lobosphaera incisa</i>
LiDGAT2.2	MH290881	<i>Lobosphaera incisa</i>
LiDGAT2.3	MH290882	<i>Lobosphaera incisa</i>
AtDGAT1	AEC06882.1	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>
ApDGAT1	KFM28983.1	<i>Auxenchlorella protothecoides</i>
BnDGAT1	AFM31262.1	<i>Brassica napus</i>
HsDGAT1	AAI50650.1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>
Pt1090DGAT1	ADY76581.1	<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>
MmDGAT1	EDL29575.1	<i>Mus musculus</i>
TpDGAT1	ADV58933.2	<i>Thalassiosira pseudonana</i>
AtDGAT2	AEE78802.1	<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>
CrDGTT1	AFB73929.1	<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>
HsDGAT2	AIC52594.1	<i>Homo sapiens</i>
MmDGAT2	EDL16367.1	<i>Mus musculus</i>
NtDGAT2	AGL46984.1	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>
Pt9DGAT2A	AFQ23660.1	<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>
Pt9DGAT2B	AFM37314.1	<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>
Pt9DGAT2C	AFQ23659.1	<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>
ScDGA1	KQC40924.1	<i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i>
AhDGAT3	AAX62735.1	<i>Arachis hypogaea</i>
VfDGAT3	AGL81309.1	<i>Vernicia fordii</i>
Ac(ADP1)1WS/DGAT	AGE15444.1	<i>Actinobacter calcoaceticus</i>